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Nod2 and AIRE exert mutual homeostatic control.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

We used a systems biologic approach to understanding homeostasis in the immune system. We identified a common regulatory network governed by two immune receptors of disparate function, Nod2 and the autoimmune regulator AIRE. A central component of homeostatic control jointly regulated by NOD2 and AIRE was the aryl hydrocarbon receptor (Ahr).

Citations

1. Schiering, C., Wincent, E., Metidji, A., Iseppon, A., Li, Y., Potocnik, A.J., Omenetti, S., Henderson, C.J., Wolf, C.R., Nebert, D.W. and Stockinger, B., 2017. Feedback control of AHR signalling regulates intestinal immunity. *Nature*, 542(7640), pp.242-245.